

ODrives

Commissioning and Software

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1. Introduction

Odrives are 2-axis drives with 120 A peak current per motor. Encoder feedback is available for arbitrarily precise movements, brake resistor and regenerative braking are possible, hardware and software are open source. Motors can be controlled in torque, velocity or position mode. Several interfaces are available, e.g. USB, UART, CAN.

Four of those drives are used to control eight motors of the platform. Following chapters explain settings and steps performed for commissioning.

2. Serial Numbers

```
static constexpr uint64_t odrive0_serialNr = 0x208c397d4d4d; // ODrive - First drive (used for testing)
static constexpr uint64_t odrive1_serialNr = 0x208A39874D4D; // ODrive1 -> M1/M2
static constexpr uint64_t odrive2_serialNr = 0x208539994D4D; // ODrive2 -> M3/M4
static constexpr uint64_t odrive3_serialNr = 0x207D396D4D4D; // ODrive3 -> M5/M6
static constexpr uint64_t odrive4_serialNr = 0x208739894D4D; // ODrive4 -> M7/M8
static constexpr float encoder_counts_per_rad = (2048 * 4) / 360.0 * (180/PI);
```

3. Settings

- Flash the firmware using '**sudo odrivetool dfu**'
- **Settings Hardware**
 - Odrv0.config.brake_resistance = 2.0
- **Settings Motor 0**
 - Odrv0.axis0.motor.config.current_lim = 10
 - Odrv0.axis0.motor.config.requested_current_range = 60
 - Odrv0.axis0.motor.config.calibration_current = 10
 - Odrv0.axis0.motor.config.pole_pairs = **14**
 - Odrv0.axis0.motor.config.torque_constant = **0.0275666 (8.27 / Kv=300)**
 - Odrv0.axis0.motor.config.motor_type = 0
- **Settings Encoder 0**
 - Odrv0.axis0.encoder.config.cpr = 8192
- **Settings Controller 0**
 - Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.vel_limit = **85.516 (5131 rpm / 60 = 85.516 turn/sec)**
- **Settings Motor 1**
 - Odrv0.axis1.motor.config.current_lim = 10
 - Odrv0.axis1.motor.config.requested_current_range = 60
 - Odrv0.axis1.motor.config.calibration_current = 10
 - Odrv0.axis1.motor.config.pole_pairs = **14**
 - Odrv0.axis1.motor.config.torque_constant = **0.0275666 (8.27 / Kv=300)**
 - Odrv0.axis1.motor.config.motor_type = 0

- **Settings Encoder 1**
 - `Odrv0.axis1.encoder.config.cpr = 8192`
- **Settings Controller 1**
 - `Odrv0.axis1.controller.config.vel_limit = 85.516 (5131 rpm / 60 = 85.516 turn/sec)`
- **Odrv0.save_configuration()**
- **Reboot**

4. Calibration

- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_FULL_CALIBRATION_SEQUENCE`
- `Odrv0.axis1.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_FULL_CALIBRATION_SEQUENCE`

5. Control mode

- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.control_mode = CTRL_MODE_VELOCITY_CONTROL`
- `Odrv0.axis1.controller.config.control_mode = CTRL_MODE_VELOCITY_CONTROL`

6. Enable drives

- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_CLOSED_LOOP_CONTROL`
- `Odrv0.axis1.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_CLOSED_LOOP_CONTROL`

7. Disable drives

- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_IDLE`
- `Odrv0.axis1.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_IDLE`

8. Tuning

- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.vel_gain = 0.45`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.pos_gain = 10.0`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.vel_integrator_gain = 0.5 * bandwidth (=1/100ms) * vel_gain = 2.25`

9. Test Tuning

Test Speed Control Loop

- **Live Plotter:** `start_liveplotter(lambda:[odrv0.axis0.encoder.vel_estimate, odrv0.axis0.controller.vel_setpoint])`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.control_mode = CTRL_MODE_VELOCITY_CONTROL`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.input_vel = odrv0.axis0.encoder.vel_estimate`
- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_CLOSED_LOOP_CONTROL`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.input_vel = 1`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.input_vel = 0`
- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_IDLE`

Test Position Control Loop

- **Live Plotter:** `start_liveplotter(lambda:[odrv0.axis0.encoder.pos_estimate, odrv0.axis0.controller.pos_setpoint])`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.config.control_mode = CTRL_MODE_POSITION_CONTROL`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.input_pos = odrv0.axis0.encoder.pos_estimate`
- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_CLOSED_LOOP_CONTROL`
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.input_pos = 1` (a number near to actual pos_estimate value)
- `Odrv0.axis0.controller.input_pos = 0`
- `Odrv0.axis0.requested_state = AXIS_STATE_IDLE`

10. Tuning Parameters

- **Vel_gain = 0.45**
- **Pos_gain = 10.0**
- **Vel_integrator_gain = 2.25**